

Simultaneous determination of praseodymium, neodymium, holmium and erbium in rare earth mixtures with ofloxacin

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A new reagent system has been developed for the simultaneous determination of praseodymium, neodymium, holmium and erbium in mixed rare earths. The method is based on the absorption spectra of 4f-electron transitions of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er complexes with ofloxacin. The second derivative spectrum has been used to eliminate the interference and to improve the sensitivity by a further factor of 2-7. Beer's law is obeyed for 7-50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er. Their relative standard deviation of the absorption signals are found to be 3.8, 2.2, 2.6 and 3.2%, respectively.

Owing to their peculiar electronic configurations ($4f^x 5s^2 p^6$), the tripositive rare earth ions render the orbital hybridizations essential to complex formation difficult to achieve. Certain chelating groups, notably the β -diketones, and 8-quinolines, however, are capable of overcoming this difficulty through the formation of inner-complex compounds. This has been used in the determination of individual REES in mixtures^{1,2}.

Ofloxacin [9-fluoro-2,3-dihydro-3-methyl-10-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-7-oxo-7H-prido[1,2,3-de]-1,4-benzoxazine-6-carboxylic acid], a fluorinated quinolone antibiotic, is widely used in the treatment of respiratory and urinary infections. It has not yet been used for the spectrophotometric determination of the rare earth elements. Here, it is found that the absorption spectra of 4f-electron transitions of praseodymium, neodymium, holmium and erbium complexes with ofloxacin are enhanced. On this basis, the spectral characteristics of the complexes and analytical application were studied. A new system has been developed for determining these four element in mixture of lanthanides by means of the second derivative spectra.

Results and Discussion

The results show that the Beer's law is obeyed in the range 5.0×10^{-5} - 3.0×10^{-4} M of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er, respectively (i.e. 7.0-42, 7.2-43, 8.2-49 and 8.4-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of final solution) and the derivative molar absorptivities are respectively 68, 150, 180 and 115 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The sensitivity is 5.4 times higher for Pr, 6.5 times for Nd, 3.4 times for Ho and 6.7 times for Er than that observed in the normal (zero derivative spectra) method.

In the system of Ln-OFLX, only Pr, Nd, Ho and Er exhibit strong 4f-electron transition peaks³. The transitions from the ground state 4H_4 of Pr^{III} ion to the 3P_2 , 1P_6 + 3P_1 and 3P_0 excited states, the ground state $^4I_{9/2}$ of Nd^{III} ion to the $^2G_{7/2}$ and $^4G_{5/2}$ excited states, the ground state 5I_8 of Ho^{III} ion to the 5G_6 excited state and the ground state $^4H_{15/2}$ of Er^{III} ion to the $^2H_{11/2}$ excited states give rise to narrow, relatively intense bands between 430 and 600 nm. The absorption spectra of aqueous solutions containing Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} and an excess of OFLX are shown in Figs. 1a-d. It can be seen that curves 1 and 2 show similar spectral features. It can be concluded that the strength of

Table 1. Spectral characteristics of different systems

Parameter	Pr ^{III}	Pr-OFLX	Nd ^{III}	Nd-OFLX	Ho ^{III}	Ho-OFLX	Er ^{III}	Er-OFLX
λ , nm	443.0	444.0	574.0	571	450.0	449.5	522.5	519.5
	467.5	469.5		581		459.5		524.4
	481.0	483.5						
ϵ , $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	12.0	12.6	6.0	22.7	4.9	52.7	2.5	17.2
	3.5	10.5		20.7		16.7		7.8
	3.2	13.0						

Fig 1 Absorption spectra of lanthanide ions and complexes $[Ln^{III}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[OFLX] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ pH = 8.6 (1) $LnCl_3$ (pH 5.6) water as reference and (2) Ln^{III} OFLX reagent blank as reference (a) Nd (b) Pr (c) Ho (d) Er

Table 2 Composition of synthetic samples and analytical results (%)

Sample no	Oxides	La ₂ O ₃	CeO ₂	Pr ₂ O ₃	Nd ₂ O ₃	Sm ₂ O ₃	Eu ₂ O ₃	Gd ₂ O ₃	Ho ₂ O ₃	Er ₂ O ₃	Y ₂ O ₃
1	Present	1.10	5.30	6.70	11.40	1.50	0.80	4.00	6.00	8.80	54.40
	Found*			6.44	11.17				5.82	9.07	
	RSD			2.8	1.9				3.4	3.2	
2	Present	22.20	34.59	7.70	15.84	1.64	1.95	1.50	5.84	6.73	1.94
	Found*			7.56	15.72				5.70	6.95	
	RSD			2.2	1.2				3.5	2.0	

* Average of five determinations RSD = relative standard deviation (n = 5)

the ionic field surrounding the rare earth ions is sufficient to penetrate the shielding effect on the *f*-electrons by the outer electrons of the ions. Therefore, the same absorption bands of 4*f*-electrons of the complexes are shifted in wavelength and enhanced in sensitivity. Table 1 gives the spectral characteristics of the systems.

The results show that the normal spectrophotometry for Pr, Nd, Ho and Er is subject to interference by the pure background absorption of the complexes. The interference of the cerium is greater compared to that of other rare earths as in other systems². Therefore, in order to eliminate the interference and improve the sensitivity, we investigated the 1st-4th derivative spectra of different lanthanide complexes and variable measuring parameters of the instrument. The optimum conditions proved to be the use of the second derivative spectra with $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm and scan rate = 20 nm/min. Fig. 2 shows the second derivative spectra of the representative lanthanide complexes. It is obvious that the optimal analytical signals are at 479.5 (+) ~ 481.5 (-) for Pr, at 566 (+) ~ 569 (-) for Nd, at 444.5 (+) ~ 446.5 (-) for Ho and at 516 (+) ~ 518 (-) nm for Er, where the other lanthanide complexes produce only a constant absorption signal, causing no interference for Pr, Nd, Ho and Er.

Fig. 2. Second derivative spectra of complexes. $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm, scan rate = 20 nm min⁻¹, other conditions as Fig. 1 curve 2, except for change in lanthanide ions: (1) La, (2) Ce^{IV}, (3) Sm, (4) Eu, (5) Er, (6) Ho, (7) Nd, (8) Pr, (9) Y, (10) Gd.

The concentration of OFLX with 1.0×10^{-4} M of Pr (Nd, Ho, Er) was optimized by varying one of them at a time. The results show that the optimal pH ranges giving

the best and most constant absorption signals are 7.2 ~ 9.2 for Nd and Pr, and 8.0 ~ 9.5 for Ho and Er; the buffer solution of pH 8.6 was chosen for subsequent experiments. Also the absorption intensity of the complexes increases with increase of OFLX concentration and then tends to be constant, reaching the strongest when the OFLX concentration is greater than 2.0×10^{-3} M. To allow for consumption of the reagent by other lanthanide ions in the mixtures, the above-mentioned amount of reagent should be increased 20-times over that necessary for the total rare earth element present. It takes 25 min to form the complex completely which is stable for at least 24 h.

The effects of common foreign ions and other lanthanide ions on the determination of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er were studied. Known amounts of foreign ions and other lanthanide ions were added to standard solution containing 80 μ g of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er in 10 ml of final solution, and then determined the their content. Tolerance limits (μ g/10 ml) with relative error $\pm 5.0\%$ of some ions are as follows: Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} (100); Ga^{III}, In^{III}, Al^{III} (40); Fe^{III}, Hg^{II}, Mn^{II} (15); La^{III}, Eu^{III}, Gd^{III}, Y^{III}, Sm^{III} (100) and Ce^{IV} (80). The larger concentration decreased the absorption signals.

Precision of the method was checked by analysis of 5.0×10^{-5} M of Pr, Nd, Ho and Er, and their relative standard deviation of the absorption signals were found to be 3.8, 2.2, 2.6 and 3.2%, respectively.

Composition of the complexes: The UV absorption maximum of the Nd complex is at 370 nm. The composition of the complex calculated by the molar ratio and continuous variations methods was found to be 1 : 2, Nd to OFLX. The results for other lanthanide complexes are similar to the neodymium complex. Hence, Ln(OFLX)₂ complex is formed in this system.

Experimental

A Simadzu UV-240 Graphicord spectrophotometer was used. The pH was measured with a pHs-2, meter (Analytical Instrument Plant, China). A 3.0×10^{-2} M aqueous solution of 9-fluoro-2,3-dihydro-3-methyl-10-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-7-oxo-7H-pyrido[1,2,3-de]-1,4-benzoxazine-6-carboxylic acid (OFLX; Qilu Pharmaceutical Plant, China) was prepared. Stock lanthanide ion solutions (0.05 M) were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of the oxides (Johnson Matthey) in 1 : 1 HCl and working solutions were prepared by dilution with water. Buffer solution of pH 8.6 was prepared using 1.0 M ammonia (37 ml) and 1.0 M ammonium chloride (163 ml).

Procedure: A known volume of the lanthanide solution was mixed with 3.0×10^{-2} M OFLX (5.0 ml) and pH 8.6

Naixing *et al* Simultaneous determination of praseodymium, neodymium, holmium and erbium in rare earth *etc* buffer solution (3.0 ml) It was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and allowed to stand for 30 min The second derivative spectra were recorded against a reagent blank as reference using 4.0 cm cells, $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm and scan rate = 20 nm/min The amplitudes were measured at 479.5 (+) ~ 481.5 (-) nm for Pr, 566 (+) ~ 569 (-) nm for Nd, 444.5 (+) ~ 446.5 (-) nm for Ho and 516 (+) ~ 518 (-) nm for Er

Application To test the utility of the method, two synthetic samples were prepared and analysed The results are listed in Table 2

In addition, two reference materials (Baotou Rare Earth Academy, China) were also analyzed for praseodymium and neodymium The results obtained were in good agree-

ment with the certified values Therefore, the accuracy and precision of the method are reasonably satisfactory

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